

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY IN DESTRUCTIVE FORMS OF ORCHIEPIDIDYMITIS

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Abstract. *The given article is dedicated to the study and analysis of the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy in the complex treatment of patients with inflammatory diseases of the scrotum. The authors present the results of treatment and comprehensive clinical-laboratory studies of 110 patients with acute orchiepididymitis from 2022 to 2024. The duration of hospitalization from the onset of the disease varied from 3 to 12 days, with an average of 5.4 ± 0.4 days. The patients ages ranged from 18 to 85 years, with an average age of 37.03 ± 3.4 years.*

Keywords: *testicular and epididymal inflammation, inflammatory diseases of the scrotum, acute and chronic epididymo-orchitis.*

Relevance:

It is important to suggest that one of the key problems in clinical urology is inflammatory diseases of the scrotal organs- acute and chronic epididymo-orchitis. They account for 4.6-10.2% of urological diseases [1,2,3,4,5]. An analysis of the literature data on the short- and long-term outcomes of conservative and surgical treatment of patients with acute inflammatory diseases of the scrotal organs indicates the insufficient effectiveness of the traditional approach to treating this disease, which necessitates the search for new pathogenetically justified methods of complex therapy [11,12,13].

In recent years, photodynamic therapy (PDT) has been actively used in the complex treatment of patients with purulent wounds of various localizations, as it offers several advantages over traditional methods of antibacterial therapy [6,7,8,9]. Considering the increase in the number of patients with purulent diseases of the scrotum, the duration of patient treatment in inpatient settings, and the growing resistance of microorganisms to the applied antibacterial drugs, the development of a new method for local therapy of inflammatory diseases of the scrotum is an important issue in modern medicine, requiring further in-depth study. This has been the basis for conducting the present study [14,15].

Study Objective is to determine the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy in the complex treatment of patients with inflammatory diseases of the scrotum.

Materials and Methods:

The present study is based on the results of treatment and comprehensive clinical-laboratory studies of 110 patients with acute orchiepididymitis between 2022 and 2024. The patients' ages ranged from 18 to 85 years, with an average age of 37.03 ± 3.4 years. The duration of hospitalization from the onset of the disease varied from 3 to 12 days, with an average of 5.4 ± 0.4 days.

Definitely, patients underwent examination of the scrotal organs, with particular attention paid to hyperemia, skin wrinkling, volume, and tenderness upon palpation of the regional lymph nodes. To assess the condition of the urogenital organs, the following methods were used:

palpation, digital rectal examination of the prostate, ultrasound (US), and color Doppler imaging of the scrotal organs, prostate, and seminal vesicles (determining sizes, echogenicity, areas of destruction, blood supply, and measuring the resistance index).

Definitely, pain symptoms were assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS). Additionally, to study the etiology of acute epididymitis, a bacteriological urine test was performed before initiating antibacterial therapy, with determination of antibiotic sensitivity.

Treatment Protocols

While prescribing medications, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory drugs were used based on the diagnostic and treatment standards recommended by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Depending on the treatment method, patients were divided into two groups. Both groups underwent surgical treatment.

- **Main Group:** 55 patients, who underwent surgical treatment on the scrotal organs with intraoperative photodynamic therapy (PDT) using a 0.05% solution of methylene blue and a red-colored LED lamp from the domestic manufacturer "VOSTOK-010203."
- **Control Group:** 55 patients who underwent surgical treatment on the scrotal organs without PDT.

Certainly, the PDT procedure was performed during the operation. After sanitation of the exudate and performing epididymotomy and/or epididymectomy, a 0.05% methylene blue photosensitizer in the amount of 20-30 ml was introduced into the scrotal cavity. The exposure was conducted for 10 minutes, and the wound was then dried.

Subsequently, irradiation was carried out using a light-emitting diode (LED) source with a wavelength of 660 ± 20 nm, produced by the "VOSTOK-010203" unit. The irradiation lasted for 5 minutes. The light source was positioned above the wound at a distance of 10 cm, and the irradiation area was 20 cm², with a radiation power of 100 W/cm² (energy density from 25 to 35 J/cm²).

Surgical Procedures

The surgical procedures were performed under local anesthesia. Various types of surgical interventions were carried out: epididymotomy, epididymectomy, and orchiectomy (Table 1). The main type of surgical treatment in both groups was epididymotomy, accounting for 92.7% and 81.8%, respectively. The indications for surgical interventions were the presence of areas of destruction in the tissues of the epididymis and the testicle itself, as well as reactive hydrocele based on ultrasound data.

Table 1

Types of surgical treatment in the examined patients

Type of Surgery	Main Group, n=55	Control Group, n=55	Total, n=110
Epididymotomy	51 (92,7%)	45 (81,8%)	96 (87,3%)
Epididymectomy	-	3 (5,4%)	3 (2,7%)
Orchiectomy	4 (7,3%)	7 (12,7%)	11(10%)

Note: $\chi^2 = 4,19, P > 0.05$

Results and Discussion

During the treatment, there was analyzed the dynamics of pain symptom changes based on the Visual Analog Scale (VAS). Before surgical treatment, the pain syndrome in both groups was

on average, 8.49 ± 0.12 and 8.44 ± 0.12 points, respectively ($P > 0.05$). As seen in Table 2, there was a significant reduction in pain syndrome in the main group over the period of observation.

Table 2

Dynamics of pain symptom changes in the patients during treatment ($M \pm m$)

Patient Groups (n=110)	Observation Time			
	2 day	4 day	6 day	8 day
Main Group (n=55)	8,36±0,14	5,64±0,08	3,04±0,08	1,11±0,04
Control Group (n=55)	9,73±0,06*	9,02±0,07*	6,73±0,10*	4,44±0,12*

Note: * $p < 0.05$ when comparing pain symptom data between groups.

Elevated body temperature values persisted for 1-2 days, and normalization of body temperature was observed on average after 1.9 ± 0.2 days (Table 3).

Table 3

Dynamics of body temperature changes depending on the treatment method

Groups (n=110)	Observation Time			
	2 day	4 day	6 day	8 day
Main Group (n=55)	38,02±0,06	37,49±0,04	37,00±0,03*	36,61±0,01
Control Group (n=55)	37,96±0,07	37,44±0,04	37,08±0,02*	36,6±0,001

Note: * $p < 0.05$ when comparing pain symptom data between patient groups.

Additionally, on the following day after PDT, most patients showed minimal discharge from the wounds, which was serous in nature. Swelling around the wounds was resolved in patients by the 2nd to 3rd day, on average after 2.7 ± 0.3 days, which was significantly better than the traditional method ($p < 0.05$).

The comprehensive treatment of patients using PDT allowed for a reduction in the duration of inpatient treatment and the complete healing time of scrotal wounds (Table 4). Thus, the patient's stay in the hospital and the overall treatment period were reduced by 28.7%.

Table 4

Duration of treatment for patients in the groups

Treatment Method	Treatment Duration (days)	
	Inpatient	Outpatient
Control Group, n= 55	8,2+1,3	7,4+1,3
Main Group, n= 55	5,3+1,1* P<0,05	4,3+1,1* P<0,05

Note: n - number of patients; * - $P < 0.05$ compared to the control group.

However, in the case of traditional treatment, a picture of a slow wound healing process with inactive reparative dynamics was observed. The use of intraoperative photodynamic therapy (PDT) leads to a reduction in the alternative-exudative phase of inflammation, alleviates microcirculatory disturbances, significantly accelerates the cleansing of wounds from purulent-necrotic masses, and promotes earlier and more active formation of granulation tissue [9].

It is important to note that in the main group of patients, the course of antibacterial therapy was comparatively shorter and did not require changes in antibacterial drugs. Furthermore, expensive reserve antibiotics were not used.

In all patients who underwent PDT, postoperative scars were elastic, not adherent to the underlying tissues, and painless. After traditional surgery, 8 (14.5%) out of 55 patients had rough scars that caused discomfort and pain.

Conclusions

By summarizing it should be suggested that the conducted study showed that the use of intraoperative PDT in the complex treatment of patients with destructive forms of orchiepididymitis leads to a rapid reduction in inflammatory manifestations around the wound and symptoms of intoxication. It is a highly effective method that allows for a reduction in the patient's hospital stay and the overall treatment duration by 28.7%. Additionally, the advantages of this method include the absence of microorganism resistance development to PDT.

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